

Measuring The Constructivist Teaching Of The Teachers Of The Departments Of Quranic Sciences And Islamic Education In Iraqi Universities

Ieman Abdul-Kareem Theeb, Alyaa Yaseen Salman

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 29, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 30, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Constructivist Teaching, Quranic Sciences, Islamic Education</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6173818</p>	<p><i>The current research aims to measure the level of teachers' teaching of the two sections of the Holy Qur'an and Islamic education in Iraqi universities. The domains are the first domain (choosing the topic of the lesson and analyzing its content) and includes (8) paragraphs, the second domain (formulation of lesson objectives) and includes (7) paragraphs, and the third domain (preparing for the situation). The activation field (which includes (11) paragraphs, the fourth field (selection of exploratory activities) and includes (13) paragraphs, the fifth field (selection of expansion activities) and includes (21) paragraphs, the sixth field (identifying and providing learning resources, materials, tools and devices) and includes (11) paragraphs and the seventh field (estimate the teaching time (which includes (8)) paragraphs, the eighth field (public relations). The physical environment is a chapter of the chapter) and includes (5) paragraphs, and the ninth field (the evaluation) includes (13) paragraphs, and the Validation of its validity by presenting it to a group of arbitrators, and the final image of the fields was reached, and it consists of (9) fields that were covered by (119) paragraphs, so that experts delete (21) paragraphs and keep (98) paragraphs distributed among all domains, and the answer to which is given five alternatives (always, often) (sometimes, rarely), never), and weight s of scores (1,2,3,4,5) for each of the alternatives, respectively. In the current scale, there are two indicators: the validity of the content and the validity of the structure. The validity of the tool was verified by two methods. The first method was the mitotic method, where the stability rates of this tool ranged between (0.71 - 0.94), and the second method was analysis. Variation using the alpha coefficient of internal consistency (0.62 - 0.93). It is a high stability coefficient, and the researcher has suggested a number of proposals as complementary studies for the current study</i></p>

Introduction

The problem of the current research appears in an attempt to reveal the constructivist teaching of teachers of the departments of Quranic sciences and Islamic education in Iraqi universities, as it cannot be directed without measuring it and knowing its degree and type. These philosophies: the constructivist philosophy that appeared in the modern era, and formed a revolution in human and social studies and ways of dealing with knowledge, and its impact extended significantly to the field of education, which contributed to the emergence of the constructivist learning theory. . Which caused a qualitative revolution in educational literature that affected all parties and forms of the educational process (students, teachers, curricula, teaching strategies), and that this expansion of information and knowledge, the spread of education, and its development. Among its institutions and the diversity of its goals, those interested in education must find modern methods and strategies in teaching and make the learner the center of the educational process, in response to the trend of modernization in the educational system in general, and my process. . This research comes to learn the Holy Quran and Islamic education and teach them in particular to determine the level of constructivist teaching among teachers of the Department of Quranic Sciences and Islamic Education in Iraqi universities as a starting point to achieve the desired change and raise the level. The educational reality in Iraqi universities.

Second:the importance of research

Emergent important research current of the importance of both of what came my

1. The university aims as one of the higher education bodies to train responsible cadres in various disciplines, prepare for different jobs, scientific research, intellectual formation, create intellectual, cultural and civilizational goods, and serve the world and the world. External environment.
2. University teaching as an extension of the chain of coherent education and its highest levels. The continuous and interactive role and responsibility among them, which it presents with accelerated and

growing movements, contributes to raising the scientific, humanitarian and national capabilities of the university.

3. Departments of Quranic sciences and Islamic education, which aim to prepare Quranic teaching sciences and Islamic education to prepare them academically, professionally and educationally to be the right place, and specialize in Quranic materials science and Islamic education as outputs qualified to lead and engage in everything. Community institutions.
4. Constructive teaching, which focuses on the process of active learning interaction where students use their previous ideas to achieve new experiences they are going through, and the teaching here is facilitating instead of the vector M Arafa, which is the active role of students in the learning process, so that the therapists are literate effective information.
5. This research provides a measure to identify the constructivist teaching practices, and the supervisor may help educators and curriculum designers to use it in evaluating the teaching behavior of teaching Quranic sciences and Islamic education.
6. Educational institutions and an appropriate educational place to generate the energies of educated students, and to introduce them to self-building according to their knowledge of the focus of constructive learning directed in line with educational development trends, according to the visions of the knowledge economy.

Third: The aim of the research

The current research aims to measure the constructivist teaching of teachers of the Noble Qur'an and Islamic education in Iraqi universities.

Fourth: Research Limits

1. The objective limit: It is represented in the knowledge of constructivist teaching among teachers of Quranic sciences and Islamic education in Iraqi universities.
2. Human limits: teachers of the departments of Quranic sciences and Islamic education in the faculties of education in Iraqi universities in the form of permanent employees.
3. Spatial boundaries: Colleges of Education at the University of Baghdad, Al-Mustansiriya University, and the Iraqi University.

Fifthly: Defining terms

First: University teaching

Teaching: He holds a master's degree or a doctorate in the disciplines of the Holy Qur'an and Islamic education, and holds a teacher's degree or above, who is entitled according to the law, and gives theoretical and applied lectures to students of primary and graduate studies and supervises them. Their research and messages in the departments of Quranic sciences and Islamic education.

Second: constructive teaching

The strategies used by the Department of Teaching Quranic Sciences and Islamic Education focus on building new knowledge in light of the t news and previous knowledge of the learner and proceed according to the stages:

1. Choosing the topic of the lesson and analyzing its content.
2. Formulating lesson objectives.
3. Preparing for the activation function.
4. Choosing the exploratory activities.
5. Selection of expansion activities.
6. Identifying and providing learning resources, materials, tools and equipment
7. Estimation of teaching time.
8. Preparing the physical environment for the class.
9. Calendar.

Third: Iraqi universities

The various educational bodies and the highest levels of scientific development, strengthen community outcomes that are capable and academically equipped in learning, scientific capabilities and equipment, and educational preparation, and grant a bachelor's degree in search of primary school.

Fourth: Department of Quranic Sciences and Islamic Education

One of the humanities departments in the faculties of education. It is an academic scientific department in which students receive the sciences of the Noble Qur'an, Islamic education and its supporting sciences, in addition to other general educational materials.

Theoretical Background

Constructive teaching

It is a process in which a comprehensive framework of steps, procedures and methods used to achieve specific goals within a specific period of time is developed and the degree to which these goals are achieved is ascertained. On the following items:

First - Choosing the topic of the lecture and analyzing its content

The educational materials that can be taught through constructivist teaching are based on some specifications, including:

1. It enables students to explore new or recent information by developing means to link them to old information stored with them.
2. Students can understand their opinions before completing the recent data.
3. Feeding students' input during teaching.
4. It contains some basic isotopes such as (recognition, classification, guessing, construction and formation) that guide students to continue the teaching process.
5. It includes information and facts about the reality of the world.
6. Supports or cooperates with the independence of the learner.
7. Strengthening interactions between students and teachers.
8. Instructing or advising students to trace the different sources.
9. Ambiguous answers to questions such as how do you study? and what do you study? .
10. Directing students to scientifically preferred sources.
11. Contains teaching strategies such as difficulty-based teaching, case study, project-based teaching, and participatory teaching.

(Habib, 2015: 41).

These specifications impose conditions on teaching a subject of his choice to be taught in a constructivist teaching:

- The topic includes a basic concept or principle, not just fragmentary facts.
- The topic is closely related to the students' personal and social lives, and is not just an academic topic within the structure of this science that has no application in their lives.
- The nature and knowledge of the subject should allow research and discovery, not be of a purely theoretical nature, or of a high level that is difficult for students to discover.
- After the teacher chooses the topic of the lecture, he analyzes its content in a number of its basic vocabulary:
- Information: facts - concepts - principles and generalizations - laws - theories...
- Skills: CognitiveApplication - analysis - aggregation - evaluation - extrapolation - subtraction...
- Nafs Kinetics: Conducting Experiments - Designing...
- Affectionate: inclinations, inclinations, interests, aspects of appreciation ...

Second - the formulation of the objectives of the lecture

Requires that the objectives of the lecture

1. Linked to the general objectives of the study stage and the course.
2. Diverse and objectives are divided into three types as follows:
 - A. Cognitive objectives
 - B. Skill goals
 - C. Emotional goals

Each of these types has levels that start from the simple level to the complex level.

3. Formulation of correct behavioral objectives) that + procedural verb + student + description of the educational experience to be mastered by the student) (A'el and Al-Menoufy, 1998 :)

Third - Preparation for the activation position

This stage aims to put the student in a teaching position that seeks to motivate him in teaching the content of the lesson and to strengthen the student's initial ideas or beliefs about this content, in addition to motivating him to work with the research efforts to be tested. His initial suspension, or the solution of a problem or problem to which he answers his work with this diligence; teaching to motivate the student to study should be planned in advance by following several methods, including:

1. Preparing a question that raises the cognitive contradiction among the students so that it appears that their information is insufficient to explain the phenomenon.
2. Preparing a practical activity that draws attention to the teacher in front of his students and then asks the students to explain this phenomenon.
3. Preparing to present to students a current event that includes a question that motivates students, activates their ideas, reveals their alternative concepts, and motivates them to participate (Al-Zaytoun, 2003). 287).

Fourth - Choosing the exploratory activities:

Since students can design their own domain experiments and infer domain rules themselves, they actually build their knowledge because of these constructive activities by experimenting with a domain and deducing rules from the results of these experiments.

Based on the foregoing, the selection of exploratory activities requires the availability of the following:-

1. To be related to the objectives of the lecture.

2. They provide real opportunities for direct sensory interaction with natural objects and phenomena, and they conduct scientific practice experiments during which they are the skills of scientific research.
3. Providing students with realistic experiences that fit their abilities and backgrounds.
4. Availability of learning resources, materials and educational tools necessary to achieve this.

(Al-Qatami, 2013: 271).

Fifth - Selection of expansion activities

These are the activities that the teacher plans for students to do to enrich their knowledge of the topic of the lecture or to apply the knowledge they have acquired in their lives and solve new problems for them. The teacher must consider fulfilling some of the following conditions in these activities:

1. Attracting students' attention in proportion to their abilities and cognitive backgrounds.
2. To be real and authentic, that is, related to their life and reality.
3. Availability of learning resources, materials and educational tools necessary to achieve them.
4. Be diverse so that students choose one or more activities to complete.

VI. Determining the sources of available educational materials, tools and devices: -

Providing learning resources, materials, tools and devices (books, references, newspapers, films, etc.) to carry out the exploration and expansion phases is essential for the success of this strategy in achieving its objectives (Al-Zaytoun, 2003). : 395).

Seventh- Estimation of Teaching Time

Builder accepts waiting time. There are those who depend or depend on students who are quick to raise their hands for an answer, and so students who are not engaged or slow in creating or preparing answers, will be enslaved from the class discussion and thus become mere spectators and do so. Don't think about the questions that the teaching asks all to get their approval of other colleagues who answer directly to the teacher, which makes the lesson not pedagogically appropriate, so students need enough waiting time to understand them because their perception of the questions may differ from what the teacher intended to ask them, and thus The teacher can give enough time to think about the questions he is asking, and ask a small group to report on the question asked, and the reports can be partial for each student individually, so the teacher gives enough time for the student to participate in the lesson in several ways (Al-Zaytoun, Al-Zaytoun, 2003 : 187).

Eighth - Creating the physical environment in the school hall

To pursue constructivist teaching, it was necessary to teach to introduce important changes and guiding principles into the curriculum, and the roles of both the teaching and the student, which required the necessity of accepting the classroom environment for building the self and the self in students and encouraging them through open-ended questions - allowing time for teaching and hoping for suggestions and answers (Jaber, 2006: 83).

Ninth - Calendar

Constructivists advocate the application and use of true assessment in teaching, a method used to comprehend, understand and evaluate the knowledge a student possesses by confronting the student and addressing problems in the world around it. The purposes of formative assessment are defined in two main areas:

Direct purposes

1. Knowing students' learning and monitoring their progress and development step by step.
2. Leading students' learning and directing them in the right direction.
3. Identifying the defect in the student's learning in preparation for linking it to the teaching staff, the student, or the curriculum.
4. Obtaining data for diagnosing the ineffectiveness of teaching.
5. Helping the teacher to improve his teaching style or finding an alternative way of teaching.
6. Reconsidering the school curriculum and modifying it if this is a factor in the lack of learning or difficulty in it.
7. Providing teachers and students with feedback on teaching and learning.
8. Develop a remedial educational plan and correct it to rid the student of weaknesses.

Indirect purpose

1. Strengthening students' motivation to learn as a result of their direct knowledge of their results and mistakes and how to correct them.
2. Learning stability or increased retention.
3. Increasing the transmission of the learning effect through the effect of the previous good learning.

Research Methodology and Procedures

First: Research Methodology

The researcher adopted the descriptive research method, because it is compatible with the nature of the research and its objectives, as it does not stop at the barriers of describing only the phenomenon, but rather goes beyond the arrangement and interpretation of data, which is evidence of the conclusions and the importance of the problem posed by them (Jaber, 1989: 134)

Second: the research community

The research community will be teaching the sciences of the Qur'an and Islamic education, and the number of (100) teachers and instructors in Baghdad governorate for the academic year (2020-2021)

Third: The research sample

The appropriate sample size for research depends on several factors in the research, such as the type of the original community, the type of research, research hypotheses, research costs, the importance of results, data collection methods, and the accuracy required in the research, and in order to limit all these factors, choosing the appropriate sample for research It requires some experience. Some of the methods for determining sample size are:

1-Tables: There are tables that determine the percentage of the sample from the original population and depend on some criteria, including the method of research, the size of the community, and researchers who are not inclined to the mathematical method benefit from it. Including a table (Krejcie& Morgan) showing the required sample size with a confidence level (0.95) and an error rate (0.05) (Appendix 3)

2-Determining the sample size using the calculator: - The special calculator can be used to determine the sample size (sample size calculator) through one of the sites that provide this service. And one of the calculator programs that provides access to the public service and accurately on the number of individuals required compared to the community, which requires filling in the blank signed as shown in the number (9), the first (confidence period (which means (degree)) of confidence) and the second) the level of confidence (ie (percentage of confidence) (error) or (the level of significance) that the researcher determines or accepts, and in order to know the required sample size for a population of (100) marks The confidence level, error rate, population size and sample size were requested through the instructions (required sample size) Was the required number (80)) The unified number d (1) The number of members of the sample (81) as a result of rounding the numbers according to the approved relative distribution that corresponds to the number extracted from the equations and tables. Accordingly, the researcher chose a sample of (81) male and female teachers using the stratified random method in public universities in the province of Baghdad, with (42) male and (39) female teachers, and the sample size represents (81%) of the original community. size

Fourth: Balance building procedures

The procedure for building any scale includes basic steps, and here is a presentation of the steps that followed to build the current scale:

Identify the basic areas of the tool

The researcher identified the fields of the questionnaire in the light of the constructivist thought literature and its foundations, and through his careful review of a large number of tools used by researchers in measuring the extent to which teachers practice constructivist teaching such as study. (Al-Saghir and Al-Nassar 2002), and (Shirfani 2009) study (Ryan 2011) (Al-Khalidi, 2013), where the researcher benefited from the opinions of some teachers when she implemented selected areas of the questionnaire. Directing an exploratory questionnaire to a sample of female teachers of Qur'anic sciences and Islamic education in Iraqi universities, numbering 15 male and female in order to identify areas of teaching constructivist in light of this has been reached to determine (9) areas were presented here on a group of experts specializing in curricula and teaching methods, psychology, measurement and evaluation numbered (22) experts, no experts object to any area of fields and as long as the scale tool Codified objectivity to measure aspects of behavior, it must represent these aspects or dimensions to be measured, and in order for this representation to be sufficient, it must have both quantitative and qualitative characteristics . In the measured function (Ahmed, 1960: 150) Accordingly, the researcher determined the relative weight of each field of the tool according to the opinions of the experts who were presented to them, and the relative weight of each field was estimated according to a seven-graded scale, and after analyzing their responses statistically using Fisher's equation (Fisher, 1957: 2) To calculate the relative weight of each field, it turns out that it varies in the strength of its measurement, then the researcher approximated the value of the relative weight to be an integer, because the number of paragraphs that will measure each field in the scale will be determined in light of the value of its relative weights, and thus the number of paragraphs of the initial image of the tool became (119). A paragraph covering (9) domains and the table showing the distribution of the scale's paragraphs on its main domains, as well as the relative weights of these domains.

The table(1)Number of fields, relative weight, and number of paragraphs for each field

number of paragraphs	relative weight	Fields	field sequence
11	9.24	Choosing the topic of the lesson and analyzing its content	1.
12	10.08	Formulate lesson objectives	2.
11	9.24	Setting the activation position	3.
16	13.45	Selection of exploratory activities	4.
25	21.01	Selection of expansion activities	5.
12	10.08	Identify and provide learning resources, materials, tools and devices	6.

12	10.08	Estimated teaching time	7.
5	4.20	Preparing the physical environment for the classroom	8.
15	12.61	Calendar	9.
	119	%100	total summation

Drafting paragraphs for each field

The researcher adopted the weights of the importance of dimensions in determining the number of paragraphs of the tool, which became calculated according to this method (119) paragraphs covering all areas of the tool, so the paragraphs were prepared by reviewing the sources and literature that were available to them, which dealt with ((constructive teaching)) or studies that looks at it or in one of its components, and has formulated a number of paragraphs based on its reading in this field.

Formulating alternatives

Five alternatives (always, often, welcome, seldom seem) were placed in front of each paragraph. Weights were assigned for scores (1, 2, 3, 4, 5) for each alternative and alternatives respectively.

Utility Tool

The purpose of preparing the instructions for the instrument is to clarify the way in which the examinee answers the paragraphs, with which he is guaranteed to get the best answer, so it was taken into account when preparing that they are simple, understandable and appropriate to the level of understanding of the sample. The actual purpose of the research was concealed in order to reduce the potential influence of the social desirability factor of social desirability.

Verify the correctness of the paragraphs of the scale

Tool G was presented as an initial tool to a group of experts specialized in the Arabic language for linguistic assessment, and the researcher took with their observations in this aspect, then presented the tool's paragraphs to a group of (22) experts in terms of reference (educational psychology, methods of teaching social studies and methods of teaching the Qur'an). The Holy Qur'an, Islamic education curricula, general teaching methods, geography teaching methods, and Arabic language teaching methods to express their views on the correctness and safety of the wording of the material). Paragraphs of the tool, the extent of the coverage of the tool, and adding, modifying or deleting any paragraph of the tool. In light of the arbitrators' opinions, (21) paragraphs were deleted with (20) paragraphs modified by experts, and (98) paragraphs were retained that constitute the final version of the tool, and were based on the standard (72.73). (%) or more as a percentage of the agreement to save, delete or modify paragraphs and based on the above paragraphs that obtained expert agreement (72.73%) at the level of significance (0.05) using the chi-square of paragraphs. Sample (Ahmed, 1989: 284) and each item were considered valid when the calculated chi-square value was a function at the level (0.05).

Correction Tool

It aims to correct the instrument to obtain the total score for the individual, and to calculate the total score of the respondent by summing the scores on all items of the measurement, in order to determine it, the five-point Likert scale (the five-point Likert scale) was adopted, given that it is rated in front of each of the items of the scale, it reflects its use Through its response to the items of the scale, and the total score for each respondent was calculated by algebraic summing of the scores of his answers on all items of the scale. The scale, in theory, the highest score a respondent can get is (49 0) and the lowest score (98).

The exploratory experience of the tool

This research aims to know the clarity of the paragraphs and instructions of the individual sample in terms of wording and meaning. The tool was applied to a random sample consisting of (5) male and (5) female teachers of the Iraqi University. The researcher herself applied the tool individually to enable them to answer the respondents' inquiries and explain to them how to answer and discuss them with clarity of instructions, paragraphs and wording, which indicates through this The application provides that the instructions and paragraphs are clear.

Statistical analysis of the tool items

The researcher analyzed the vocabulary statistically to reveal its validity or homogeneity in order to preserve the good items and to reveal its accuracy in the scale in measuring what was prepared for measurement and to verify its efficiency in achieving the principle of individual differences because the aim of this analysis is to retain the valid items in the scale and to exclude or modify invalid items . The researcher followed two methods that are not a result of the analysis process, they are the method of the last two extremes, and the relationship between the degree of the total paragraph and each paragraph of the values is indicative of the paragraphs of both directions.

Psychometric indicators of the tool

1. Honesty: - Providing indicators for the current scale are the validity of the content and building honesty or internal consistency

- The reliability tool: Two methods T were adopted, the middle-range segmentation method and the B method to analyze variance using the Facronbach coefficient equation, where the reliability coefficient for the scale as a whole was (0.93), (0.94), respectively, which is the stability of the accepted coefficients for research purposes, and it was judged using the absolute criterion by squaring the computed reliability coefficient (Al-Bayati and Athanasius, 1977: 194)

General description of the tool

- In its final form, the scale consists of (98) items covering (9) domains, where the first domain (8) items, the second domain (7), the third domain (11) and the fourth domain (13) and the fifth domain (21) and the domain of Sixth (11) and seventh (9), eighth (5) and ninth (13) paragraphs.
- Given paragraphs (5) alternatives to answer a (always, often, welcome, rarely, a), the weights were determined as degrees (1, 2, 3, 4, 5) for each of the alternatives and, respectively, Thus, the highest degree of the ladder is (490 degrees) and the lowest degree is (98) degrees with an average of (294) degrees.

Application procedures

After confirming the tool's honesty and stability, it was electronically designed in the researcher Tan to send the scale to the research sample by publishing questionnaires via social media applications such as: Twitter, Facebook, as well as copies of the form and sending it via WhatsApp link to AB and after retrieval of the questionnaires and adults, their number (81) As a teacher of Quranic sciences and Islamic education, the researcher emptied the questionnaire data into special tables prepared for this purpose. Ready for statistical analyses.

Fifth: Statistical Means

The researcher used the statistical package for social sciences (Spss) for the purpose of processing statistical data and extracting the results- :

- Chi-square test for a single sample test (χ^2)
- Pearson correlation coefficient: the individuals correlation coefficient
- The Spearman-Brown equation
- Cronbach's alpha equation (Cronbach's alpha formula)
- Weighted average
- Weight percentile of the vertebra
- T test for two independent samples of equal size
- One-way ANOVA

Chapter Four: Presentation and Interpretation of Results

This chapter includes what the researcher has reached according to his objectives, discussing those results and then making recommendations and suggestions based on those results. In order to interpret the results, the researcher transformed the Likert scale into five periods of equal length (0.8), and the judgment is based on the extent to which constructivist teaching is used in whole or in part while teaching students of Quranic science and Islamic education departments according to the lower and upper limits of Likert scale and the corresponding percentage for each cell and the degree of use As shown in the table

Table(2)The lower and upper limits of the Likert scale, the corresponding percentage of each cell, and the degree of use

degree of use	percentage	Average
Very weak	%35-%20	from 1-1.7
weak	%51-%36	From 1.8-2.5
medium	%67-%52	3,3-2,6
High	%83-%68	4,1-3,4
very high	%100-%84	5-4.2

The results will be presented according to the research objectives defined in the first chapter, and 25% of the structural education used, ranked highest and lowest, will be discussed and explained. Knowing the extent to which the teaching of Quranic sciences and Islamic education is used to teach constructivism in Iraqi universities To achieve this goal, the researchers calculated the frequency and weighted average of the percentage weight for all paragraphs of the scale for each strategy on the use of the Holy Qur'an and Islamic education sciences for constructivist teaching in Iraqi universities. The results were as follows:

First - Choosing the topic of the lecture and analyzing its content: - They were very high in paragraphs (1,2) where their weighted averages ranged (4.40, 4.3) and weight percentiles (88, 86) and were high in paragraphs (3), 4, 5, 6, 7, 8) and their weighted value (3.93, 4.02, 4.15, 3.77), 4.12, 4.06) and weight percentile (78.6, 80.4, 83, 75.4, 82.4, 81.2) and was high in the field as a whole where the weighted mean (4.09) and weight percentile (81.8), indicating that the lecture topic selection score is used and the analysis of its content to a high degree by the professors of the departments of Quranic sciences and Islamic education.

Second - Formulating the objectives of the lecture: - It was high in all paragraphs, as its weighted averages ranged between (3.93 - 4.15) and the percentage of weights (78.6 - 83), and it was high in the field as a whole,

where it was weighted. The average was (4.07) and the weight percentage was (81.4) which indicate that the formulation of the lecture objectives: The lecture objectives are used to a high degree by the teachers of the departments of Quranic sciences and Islamic education.

Third - Preparation for the activation position: - It was very high in paragraphs (16, 17, 19, 20, 21, 23) as its weighted averages ranged (4.31, 4.22, 4.33, 4.49, 4.51, 4.31) and weight. The percentages (86.2, 84.4, 86.6), 89.8, 90.2, 86.2) were high in items (18, 22, 24, 25) with weighted averages (4.14, 3.99, 4.02, 4.17) and weight percentages (82.8, 79.8), 80.4, 83.4) and it was medium in item (26). Her weighted average was (3) and her weight percentile (60) and she was high in the field as a whole. The mean weight was (4.14) and its weight percentile was (82.8), which indicates that it was used with a high degree of preparation to activate the function by teachers of the departments of Quranic sciences and Islamic education.

Fourth - the selection of exploratory activities: - They were high in paragraphs (27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 35, 36, 39) where their averages ranged (4.14, 3.75, 4, 3.99). (4.2, 4.05, 3.95). , 3.94, 3.83, 4.01 (and weight percentile) 82.8, 75, 80, 79.8, 84, 81, 79, 78.8, 76.6, 80.2 respectively, and it was very high in the paragraphs (34, 37, 38), like and its weighted meaning was (4.28). , 4.32, 4.4) and weight percentile (85.6, 86.4, 88) respectively, and were high in the field as a whole with a weighted average (4.07) and weight percentile (81.4), which indicates that the selection of exploratory activities is highly used by the professors of science departments The Qur'an and Islamic Education.

Fifthly - the selection of expansion activities: - It was high in paragraphs (40, 43, 44, 45, 46, 49, 50, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 59, 60) with weighted averages ranging between (3.58-4.17) and a percentage of Weight (71.6 - 83.4) while it was very high on cultivars (41, 42, 47, 48, 51, 57, 58), where their average weight ranged (4.21 - 4.41) and weight ratio. (84.2 - 88.2) and was high in the field as a whole, with its weighted average (4.08) and weight ratio (81.6), which indicates that the selection of expansion activities is highly used by department teachers. Quranic sciences and Islamic education.

Sixth - Determining and providing learning resources, materials, tools and devices: they were high in paragraphs (61, 62, 63, 67, 68, 69, 71) and their weighted averages ranged (3.94, 4.1, 3.59). , 4.16 3.98, 3.8, 3.98) and weight percentile (78.8, 82, 71.8, 83.2, 79.6, 76, 79.6) and was very high in paragraph (70), with its weighted mean (4.43) and weight percentile (88.6).), and it was average in paragraphs (64, 65, 66), where its average weight was (3.06, 2.88, 2.89) and weight ratio (61.2, 57.6). , 57.8) and was high in the field as a whole, with a weighted average of (3.71) and a weight ratio of (74.2), which indicates that the identification and provision of learning resources, materials, tools and devices was high. Degree by teachers of the departments of Quranic sciences and Islamic education.

Seventh- Estimation of teaching time: It was high in the paragraphs of this field of the sequence (72, 73, 74, 75, 76, 77, 80), where their weighted averages ranged between (3.53 - 4.04) and.Eight percent (70.6 - 80.8) excluding paragraph (79). It was very high with a weighted average (4.37) and a weight ratio (87.4), and it was medium in paragraph (78), where its weight averages ranged (2.88) and (57.6) and it was high. In the field as a whole, with a weighted average of (3.72) and a weight of (74.4), which indicates the interest of teachers of the departments of Quranic sciences and Islamic education in estimating teaching time. • While teaching the courses of the Department of Quranic Sciences and Islamic Education in the Colleges of Education

Eighth - Preparing the physical environment for the class: - It was high in all items with a weighted average that ranged between (3.7 -4.17) and a weight ratio (74 - 83.4) and it was very high in the field as a whole as a weighted average. It reached (3.94) and a weight ratio of (78.8), which indicates that the teachers of the Holy Qur'an and Islamic education departments are very interested in preparing the physical environment for the classroom in the teaching of the Qur'an department courses. Science and Islamic Education in the Faculties of Education.

Ninth- Evaluation: It was very high on the cultivars (86, 87, 94, 95) with an average weight (4.37, 4.22, 4.37, 4.22) and a percentage weight (87.4, 84.4, 87.4, 84.4). They were high in items (88, 89, 90, 91, 92, 93, 96, 97, 98) where their weighted averages were (4.14, 4.01, 3.94, 3.89, 3.88, 4.17, 4.14, 4.01, 3.94) and the weight percentage (82.72, 80.2, 78.8, 77.8, 77.6, 83.4, 82.8, 80.2, 78.8) and it was high in the field as a whole, where its weighted average was (4.1) and with a weight percentage (82), which indicates that the professors of Quranic sciences and Islamic education departments pay The importance of evaluation in teaching the courses of the Department of Quranic Sciences and Islamic Education in the Colleges of Education.

The researcher believes that to complete the picture of constructivist teaching, it must be arranged according to the arithmetic averages, as shown in the table

table(3)Descending order of constructivist teaching used in teaching Quranic sciences and Islamic education according to their field, arithmetic averages and percentage weights for the sample as a whole (n = 81)

ranking	Availability	weight percentile	average	constructivist teaching
3	High	81.8	4.09	Choosing the topic of the lecture and analyzing its content
5	High	81.4	4.07	Formulate the objectives of the lecture

1	High	82.8	4.14	Setting the activation position
5	High	81.4	4.07	Selection of exploratory activities
4	High	81.6	4.08	Selection of expansion activities
8	High	74.2	3.71	Identify and provide learning resources, materials, tools and devices
7	High	74.4	3.72	Estimated teaching time
6	High	78.8	3.94	Preparing the physical environment for the classroom
2	High	82	4.1	Calendar
	High	79.8	3.99	Overall score in all fields

It is clear from the table () that shows the arithmetic averages and the weighted percentage of the estimates of the members of the research community on the constructivist teaching included in the study tool, as follows: - He got the first place through (preparation for the study). Activation position) with its weighted mean (4.14) and weight percentile (82.8%), followed by second place (assessment) with its weighted mean (4.1) and weight percentile (82%), followed by third place. Rank (selection of the lecture topic and analysis of its content) with a weighted average of (4.09) and percentage of weight (81.8%), then it came in fourth place (selection of expansion activities) with a weighted average of (4.08). The percentile weight (81.6), followed in the fifth place (formulation of lecture objectives) and (selection of exploratory activities), where its weighted average reached (4.07) and percentile weight (81.4) and then came in rank. Sixth (preparation en viro physical grew class) with a weighted average (3.94) and weight ratio (78.8), then ranked seventh (teaching time estimate) with a weighted average (3.72) and weight ratio (74.4). then it was followed in eighth place (identifying and providing learning resources, materials, tools and devices) with a weighted average of (3.71) and a weight of (74.2), and in terms of the total score in all areas. It was high with an overall weighted average of (3.99) and a score of (79.8%)

Interpretation of results

First place: (preparation for the stimulating situation) This can be attributed to the importance of this field in arranging all learning processes, as numbers reduce effort and effort, save time and raise learning efficiency, especially since teachers are trying. To put students in a teaching position that seeks to raise their motivations and strengthen their ideas, and to form trends that can be described as being in line with constructivist ideas in terms of making the learner the main pillar or axis of the learning process, and the resulting change in the strategies of the educational process. Towards specific issues they are interested in, as I got a weighted average (4.51) and weight percentile (90.2), and employing investigation questions gradually and continuously, where I got a weighted average (4.49) and weight percentage (89.8), and choosing questions with levels of thinking It obtained the weighted average (3.99) and the weight of the percentage (79.8), and based on the procedural educational activities. It fits with the goals, content and nature of the students, as it obtained a weighted average (3) and a weight ratio (60), and it is believed that these practices are necessary to implement constructivist teaching, which is the preparation of concepts to be learned and linking learning to life by choosing roles from students' lives, and constitute The learning environment is a situation for preparing the lecture before it begins in order to retrieve the information. On stored by students.

Second place: (Evaluation): - This result can be attributed to the clarity of its goal among teachers of Quranic sciences and Islamic education, as it represents an essential part of the educational process to know the extent to which students understand the material. In addition to the extent to which they perceive the process as a coherent and interconnected part of the educational process as a whole in order to know the changes. The method was added to the student's experiences (Abu Odeh, 2006:24), and the assessment cannot be considered a standalone or separate summary of course completion. , 2012: 89), two paragraphs: setting tests according to scientific standards, and preparing tests that are compatible with the nature of the educational material on a weighted average (4.37) and a weight ratio (87.41). (4.22) and (84.44) weight percentile. Students are encouraged to explain their learning results to the rest of the students and to involve them with their peers in the assessment process on a weighted mean (3.94) and weight percentile (78.77) seventh rank: domain (teaching rating). time): This field can be explained by the fact that constructivist teaching depends to a large extent on the time available to teach, as most of the phases of teaching are not set in a specific time for completion, which makes estimating this time difficult for him. The teacher, especially if there are skills students work outside of the classroom, the teacher evaluates his lecture time based on his teaching information and divides the time through the educational stages related to constructivist teaching. in its presentationThe measures adopted by constructivist teaching are to give students sufficient time to speak and engage in the learning process, having a weighted average score of (3.65) and a relative weight of (73), and to give students the opportunity to build and realize relationships. And find similes and metaphors, if they get a weighted average (4.04) and a weight percentage (80.8) and give the students the largest role in managing the lesson, where they get a weighted average (2.88) and a weight percentage (57.6), and direct the students to an investment The lesson time seriously, as they obtained a weighted average (3.44) and a weight ratio (68.8)

Eighth place: (identifying and providing learning resources, tools, and devices): This may be due to the lack of attention and focus on this area or component by the educational staff, as students hope that the exploratory and expansive activities will be. Returning to the educational resources consisting of (books, films, newspapers, as well as references.....etc) to obtain or possess all experience relating to the problem, and most often it requires tools, materials and devices in order to complete it, which requires prior preparation It (Hassan and Zeitoun, 2003: 387-395), and the paragraph (organizing visits to some prominent figures in the community) got a weighted average of (4.43) and a weight ratio (88.64), and the paragraph (the use of materials available in the learning environment in addition to the content tabular) on a weighted average (4.16) and weight ratio (83.21), the paragraph (interest in applied learning using modern technologies) on a weighted average. (3.98) and weight ratio (79.51), and the paragraph (providing different sources of ICT tools for the necessity of explanation) on the weighted average (2.89) and weight percentile (57.78), which explains why. The fact that this domain ranked last, the overall score across all domains was high with a weighted average of (3.99) and a weight percentile (79.8%). , such as transactions, worship and morals, which make the learning process enjoyable and practical, and students play a prominent focus in it, sometimes through teamwork, praxis, simulation, and representation On the other hand, problem solving and learning by observation, and thirdly, which highlights on the role of teachers as facilitators and facilitators. It is directed to the learning process, and away from the exercise of the traditional role in teaching.

Second :Conclusions

In light of the results that have been reached, the researcher reached the following conclusions:-

1. It turns out that the total degree of the use of teachers of Quranic sciences and Islamic education for constructivist teaching was a high percentage.
2. All areas (choosing the topic of the lecture and analyzing its content, formulating the objectives of the lecture, preparing for the activation situation, choosing exploratory activities, choosing expansion activities, determining and providing learning sources, materials, tools and devices, estimating teaching time, preparing the physical environment of the classroom, evaluation) got a degree. High

Third: Recommendations

Through the research results, the researcher reached the following recommendations

1. The Islamic education curricula include applied models for lessons based on the strategies of constructivist theory ;for teachers to benefit from in their teaching.
2. Reconsidering the preparation of teachers of Islamic education and the Holy Qur'an and trying to add courses that emphasize the foundations of constructivism and its educational applications in the constructivist teaching system in the programs of the colleges of education and basic education.
3. Inclusion of applied models and lessons in the curricula of Quranic sciences and Islamic education based on the strategies of constructivist theory, especially constructivist teaching.
4. Reunification of constructivist teaching in the general and specific objectives of the subjects of the Holy Qur'an sciences and Islamic education.
5. Reconsidering the books of Islamic education and the Noble Qur'an by organizing and arranging their content in a manner that is commensurate and consistent

With Strategies of Constructivist Theory

Fourth: Suggestions

The researcher suggests conducting the following studies as complementary studies to the current research:

1. Evaluating Islamic education books and the Noble Qur'an at the primary stage in light of the requirements of constructivist teaching .
2. The role of using constructivist teaching strategies in achieving the objectives of Islamic education books and the Noble Qur'an from the point of view of teachers and supervisors.
3. The effectiveness of a proposed training program for developing the skills of constructivist teaching among teachers of the Holy Qur'an and Islamic education and measuring its impact on learners.
4. The effectiveness of teaching and learning based on constructivist theory in developing Islamic education teaching practices for the preparatory stage.

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Author Information

Prof. Ieman Abdul-Kareem Theeb

College of Education for Girls, Iraqi University, Iraq

Alyaa Yaseen Salman

College of Education for Girls, Iraqi University, Iraq
